

THE INDIVIDUAL'S REACTION TO INFORMATION OVERLOAD AND THE NEED FOR SEGMENTATION THROUGH PSYCHOGRAPHIC PROFILES

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Abstract

The electronic stage of communication has put the individual's consciousness in conditions of extreme overload. The human nervous system is not able to process the enormous amount of information. In order to function normally, a person must have ways to 'sift' it, focusing their attention on only a part of it. The hypothesis is that due to their psychological specifics, users form groups with similar features of information acceptance.

In order to verify the existence of such groups and to highlight their characteristics, in the period 2001-2023, more than 130 quantitative surveys were conducted, nationally representative of the country's population or certain groups of it, by the method of direct personal interviews with the application of an identical set of indicators, allowing through correlation, factor and cluster analyses to distinguish the groups according to the Psychographic Profiles. As a result, 4 groups were found, identical for Bulgaria and for other countries, which react to information in a similar way by directing their attention to that part of it that most fully corresponds to the essence of the personality. This made it possible for entities producing information — companies, state and public structures — to refine their communication, make it more effective and more economical by orienting it towards a dominant Psychographic Profile for their purposes.

Keywords: *Psychographic profiles; psychology; segmentation; communication; information overload; psychography; consumer behavior; longitudinal research; Bulgaria*

Introduction

One of the main difficulties in the contemporary world experienced by all entities that produce and disseminate information is how to make the individual, amidst the quadrillions of information elements,

pay attention precisely to what they are broadcasting. Based on one of the main psychological conclusions — that every individual strives to achieve the greatest possible balance between the challenge (in this case — the mountains of information) and their own abilities to receive and process this information — the possibility was explored for individual persons to be actually 'included' in groups according to the general characteristics of the personality in relation to the perception of information.

The effect of information overload has been unambiguously described by psychologists: "Information overload occurs when the volume of information offered exceeds the limited human capacity to process information. The result is dysfunctional effects such as stress and confusion." (Eppler & Mengis, 2004) The individual is therefore forced to find ways through which — in a continuum and not sporadically — to cope with the problem.

The aim of the present work is to explore the probability of the existence of a clearly expressed structuring of the population according to Psychographic Profiles, which allows information directed at the individual to be produced and disseminated much more effectively, by being created and oriented toward a certain group according to these profiles that would most willingly admit it into their consciousness.

The Benefits and Negatives of the Infinite Amount of Information

The electronic stage of communication (the fifth in the history of civilization, according to Logan) confronted human individuals with a new, cardinal problem: how to function effectively under the totally disseminated and unceasing stream of information. Never before in the history of human civilization has the individual been confronted with such a challenge.

Paul Hemp colorfully noted as early as 2009 in his piece "Death by Information Overload": "The flow of information that floods me every day seems to cause me more pain than bring me profit. And not only the incoming tidal wave of email messages and RSS feeds causes me anguish. It is also the vast ocean of information I feel compelled to explore in order to keep working." (Hemp, 2024)

The obvious limits of the human individual's ability to process information are well known: "Our nervous system is not capable of processing more than 110 bits of information per second. Just to hear me and understand what I'm saying, you need to process 60 bits per second. That's why you can't understand more than two people talking to you at the same time." (Csikszentmihalyi, 2024)

In contemporary conditions, at one and the same moment an individual is being "spoken to" simultaneously by far more than two people. This gave Zygmunt Bauman grounds to summarize: "The possibilities of informal communication have remained largely unchanged since at least the Paleolithic, and cheap communication floods and suffocates memory, instead of nourishing and stabilizing it." (Bauman, 1998) Psychologists register that consciousness is the complex system that has evolved in humans to select information from this abundance, process it, and store it through the selective investment of attention. (Nakamura & Csikszentmihalyi, 2014)

Subjected to the incessant informational pressure, the individual is compelled to find a way to navigate the ever-growing number of information sources. It is illogical to assume that billions of individuals react in their own unique way to this challenge. It is more plausible to seek options showing that in communities there are clearly differentiated groups that in a similar way interact with information.

The Methodology for Defining Population Groups According to Psychographic Profiles

The creation of the set of indicators — formulation, testing, correction — took 14 years, starting from 2001, and several dozen nationally representative surveys of the adult population of Bulgaria, each conducted by the method of direct personal interviews by Progress Consult (established in 1996). Since 2015, this methodology has been intensively used in dozens of projects in practice.

After creating the productive set of indicators, the analyses of the results very quickly showed that users actually concentrate in only 4 groups according to their Psychographic Profiles. Each of these groups

has a different combination of traits, but each group can also contain within itself some of the traits belonging to people from other groups. Such "overlapping" of segments is very useful from the perspective of communication, because whenever a given group is defined as a primary target of some communication, there is at least one more group in which some of its traits are also present.

The Four Groups According to the Psychographic Profiles and Their Main Characteristics

The following ratio between groups was registered in the structure of the adult population of Bulgaria (Figure 1) (data from a nationally representative survey, direct personal interviews, n=1030, November 2019 — one of the last "calm" moments before the period of global cataclysms that began with the COVID-19 pandemic):

Figure 1. Groups According to Psychographic Profiles — as % of the adult population of Bulgaria. Source: Progress Consult, nationally representative survey, direct personal interviews, n=1030 (November 2019).

Specific features of each group:

SEEKERS

Emotions are one of the most strongly distinguishing features: no other group has members who experience such a high degree of desire to indulge in pleasures and excitements (and therefore to pay for them). Due to the fact that they are the most willing to take risks and with the highest degree of self-confidence, Seekers have the greatest desire of all to try new things. They tend toward collectivism — they feel very comfortable in a group. The opinions of others are not decisive, but nonetheless important to them.

MEMBERS

They seek mostly warm relationships with others. Emotions and pleasures in life are not the most essential thing for them. The essential thing is to have their right to hold their own opinion recognized, to be "heard" — although they are then inclined to accept the position of the referent or the group. They prefer comfort — including in group relations — over creating difficulties, striving in every way to avoid "scenes" of clashes and confrontation. In counterpoint, they orient themselves toward the "leisurely" in life, which offers ease and relief.

SOLITARY

To the lowest degree of all, they are interested in the opinions of others. Absolutely convinced of their sole rightness, their own opinion is for them an irrefutable law. They are not interested in whether others respect them or whether they will have good relations with them. Led by the understanding that rightness is always on their side, they experience a high degree of a sense of superiority over "others." This is why they are attracted to sharper clashes and clearly expressed confrontation.

BALL BEARINGS

The most insecure and cautious of all. The absolute prerequisite for them is to feel a sense of security by fitting into a group. They show the most pronounced tendency among all to comply with the opinions of others (referents). The key concept for them is Security. They are the most cautious group of consumers, combining very hard time taking any risks with comparatively low self-confidence.

Psychographic Profiles and the Broadcasters of Information

Grouping according to Psychographic Profiles represents a structuring according to the presence of similar traits in the essence of individual personalities. These traits manifest in preferences for certain product or price categories, specific brands, cultural phenomena, and mass media. Every brand "draws" toward itself precisely certain consumers who belong to a greater extent to a given group according to Psychographic Profiles — identifying the source as "like themselves" and "attaching" to it together with other "like themselves."

Psychographic Profiles and the "Tangible"

In something so connected to everyday life — fueling at gas stations (data from a nationally representative survey of adult citizens of Bulgaria using automobiles, direct personal interviews, n=994, December 2016) — Figure 2, we find differentiated attitudes of each group toward each chain:

Figure 2. Preferred Gas Station Chain — as % of the respective group according to Psychographic Profiles. Source: Progress Consult, nationally representative survey of adult population of Bulgaria using automobiles, direct personal interviews, n=994 (December 2016).

The data crystal-clearly show that Lukoil's signals are "read" to the highest degree by Seekers, Petrol's signals — to a drastically higher degree than the others by Ball Bearings, and OMV's signals — by the Solitary. This is categorical evidence that the individual entities had fundamentally different communication schemes and for this reason they were "read" by entirely different groups of consumers.

Looking at specific product brands — regardless of whether they are vitamins, cheese, or cigarettes — Figure 3 (data from a nationally representative survey of adult citizens of Bulgaria, direct personal interviews, n=998, August 2014), we find the same differentiated attitude. It does not matter whether the respective brand is the market leader or a player with medium market weight: in all cases the degree of attraction of individual Psychographic groups differs for each brand:

Figure 3. Preferred Cigarette Brand — as % of the respective group according to Psychographic Profiles. Source: Progress Consult, nationally representative survey of adult population of Bulgaria, direct personal interviews, n=998 (August 2014).

Psychographic Profiles and the "Intangible"

In 2017, the methodology for defining population groups according to their Psychographic Profiles was implemented in the Nielsen Admosphere peplemeter system in Bulgaria at the suggestion of media agency Argent. The panelists were individually defined as belonging to a specific Psychographic Profile. This made it possible to observe with complete objectivity what the preferences of viewers from each group were toward specific television channels, types of programs, and specific programs — Figure 4 (data from a nationally representative survey conducted jointly by Progress Consult and Nielsen Admosphere, 2018):

Figure 4. Audience Share in % — Feature Film on Sunday, 8:00 PM: Shakespeare in Love (romantic comedy, bTV) vs. Mission Impossible — Phantom Mode (spy action, NOVA). Source: Nielsen Admosphere / Progress Consult, 2018.

Among the Solitary in particular, even greater interest toward the action film was observed — which is in complete accordance with their profile. Being extraordinarily self-convinced of their original rightness, they enjoy watching battles and clashes. Exactly the opposite is the behavior of the Members — the only group that in greater part chose the romantic comedy, in full accord with their desire to "be left in peace" and avoid any form of tension.

The approach of focusing primarily on Psychographic Profiles is proving ever more productive. Ward, De Neve, Ungar and Eichstaedt's analysis of the 2016 US presidential elections concluded: "The economic and psychological processes established earlier have in common that they generated or electorally capitalized on unhappiness in the electorate, which emerges as a powerful high-level predictor of the 2016 electoral outcome." (Ward et al., 2024) Psychological processes — not

demographic characteristics — become a "powerful predictor." And this means that successful psychographic segmentation of the population enables composing information that will be perceived with greater willingness and prompt predictable actions.

Conclusion

The longitudinal surveys of the population made it possible to establish the mechanisms through which individuals cope with the problem of information overload in the present era. A structure of consumers according to their Psychographic Profiles was successfully derived, and the specifics of each of these groups determine whether and to what extent the representatives of each profile open their communication channels to specific incoming information.

This mechanism is independent of the sphere to which the broadcasters of information belong: it is activated in the same way with respect to any information incoming to the individual. Such a characteristic allows the individual to more successfully "sift" the messages directed at them, and the broadcasters of information to communicate more effectively with consumers, taking into account the specifics of the group according to Psychographic Profiles that represents dominant interest for them.

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About the Author

Rossen Koutelov is Doctor of Sociology (UNWE Sofia, 2025) and founder of Progress Consult (est. 1996). His doctoral dissertation "Psychographic Profiles and Consumer Behavior" developed an original longitudinal methodology validated through 13 nationally representative surveys (n=12,904, Bulgaria 2013-2023), identifying four stable psychographic groups: Seekers, Members, Solitary, and Ball Bearings.

This paper presents the first published account of applying the psychographic segmentation methodology to consumer brand preferences across multiple sectors — gas stations, cigarette brands, and media consumption — demonstrating the universal cross-domain validity of the psychographic filter mechanism.

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